

Dissociative excitation of acetone induced by electron impact

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September 2024

Abstract. We report the results of an experimental study focused on the low-energy (10-100 eV) electron impact excitation of acetone. In the emission spectrum, the most prominent excited species were found to be the hydrogen Balmer series, the excited CH radical in the A and B electronic states, and atomic carbon. The presence of OH emission in the spectra confirms the tautomerization process induced by electron impact. The acetone emission spectra were measured at several different reaction energies, forming a unique 3D spectral electron energy map. Excitation-emission functions were determined for selected most prominent products.

1. Introduction

Acetone is a compound commonly used as a solvent in paints, drugs and other chemicals due to its miscibility with water, alcohol and most oils. It can also be used as a dehydrating agent [1]. It is an omnipresent atmospheric gas that has a significant impact on atmospheric chemistry, especially on the concentration of other species that can degrade greenhouse gases such as methane. Acetone-initiated reactions can also influence atmospheric oxidants levels and ozone formation [?]. It is also one of the organic compounds that can be found in outer space. Its detection in the interstellar space was first reported by [?]. The NRAO 12 m telescope was used in 2002 to detect 13 acetone emission features and confirm the interstellar acetone identification made by Combes et al. in 1987 [2]. Acetone has also been proven to be abundant in the mass spectra from 67P/Churyumov Gerasimenko, detected by the COSAC mass spectrometer on the comet's surface [3, 4]. The abundances of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$ and other organic compounds in the protoplanetary disk around V883 Ori were reported by [5]. In space electron impact processes play a significant role in various different environments [6, 7] therefore, it is necessary to understand the kinetics of electron-impact reactions on acetone. For applications in astronomy especially emission spectra need to be well described as most astronomical objects can be studied mainly by means of emission spectroscopy. The type of excitation process can significantly affect the emission

spectrum [8]. As a result, the shape of the spectrum may indicate whether the emission is induced by electrons, photons, or other sources, and provide insights into the excitation reaction energy. There are no known studies on the fluorescence of acetone induced by electron impact. However, several publications have examined the fluorescence of acetone induced by other sources. Laser induced fluorescence was studied by [9, 10]. Thurber et al. [10] investigated the wavelength-dependent variations of acetone fluorescence with temperature at atmospheric pressure. N. Wermuth and V. Sick [9] determined the absorption cross-sections and fluorescence quantum yields. In 2013 Tang et al., [11] presented a spectral diagnosis of acetone in atmospheric pressure argon/acetone plasma jet. This study provided optical emission spectra of acetone and argon species, which are important to the concept of plasma polymerization of volatile organic reagents. Acetone has also been studied extensively by electron energy loss spectroscopy. Several publications are focused on electronic and vibrational excitations of acetone in condensed and vaporised state. High resolution electron energy loss spectra of acetone for 100 eV incident electrons scattered at zero angle were obtained by [12] and scattering angles from 0° to 90° were investigated by [13]. They provide identification of singlet and triplet states as well as some Rydberg states. Low-energy electron-energy-loss spectroscopy of solid films of acetone [14] shows that the Rydberg progression completely disappears in solid state and valence electronic transitions are dominant. This paper is focused on dissociative electron impact excitation of acetone at low electron energies up to 100 eV.

2. Experimental apparatus

The experiment performed in this work is based on a crossed electron and molecular beams method, which is further described in a previous publication [15]. Trochoidal electron monochromator (TEM) is used to generate an electron beam with well-defined energy ranging from 0 to 100 eV. The energy resolution of the electrons is up to 300 meV FWHM depending on the used settings. The electron beam interacts with a molecular beam formed by an effusive capillary with the diameter of 0.5 mm. The background pressure of the vacuum chamber is 10^{-8} mbar and the pressure of the molecular beam is set to sustain binary interactions to avoid further interaction of scattered electrons with the beam. The electron and molecular beams collide perpendicularly to each other and generate various products such as excited particles, which are the subject of this research. An optical system consisting of a plano-convex UV fused silica lens, an MgF_2 window and a parabolic mirror is used to guide the emitted photons out of the vacuum chamber and focus them into the entrance slit of a Czerny-Turner 0.25 m monochromator with a resolution of up to 0.4 nm. A spherical mirror, having the focus at the centre of collision, is mounted opposite to the collecting lens to maximise the collected signal. Two detectors - a Hamamatsu photomultiplier (PMT) or a CCD (CCD) camera are used for the detection and quantification of the emission passing through the optical monochromator. The photomultiplier is cooled by an air-cooled Peltier module to -15°C and operates in the wavelength region of 185 – 700 nm. It collects the signal from one small wavelength interval defined by optical resolution of the monochromator at a time. The CCD camera is cooled

to -100 °C by a liquid cooling system and a Peltier module and is sensitive in 270 – 1100 nm wavelength range. It detects light from approximately 80 nm wide wavelength interval at once which makes it more time-efficient for measuring emission spectra. The CCD camera and its operation was further described in Blaško et al. [16]. The scheme of the experimental apparatus is shown in Fig. 1.

The measured data were processed and analyzed in several steps. First, the calibration of electron energy was done by measuring the energy-dependent cross section of He I ($1s2p^3P_{1,2}^3 - 1s4d^3D_{1,2,3}$) emission line at 447.14 nm. This cross section has a well-defined threshold at 23.736 eV [17]. After the electron energy calibration, the spectra were corrected for the spectral sensitivity of the experimental apparatus. The intensity scale of the spectra is relative.

3. Experimental results

The emission spectrum containing dissociated fragments of acetone was obtained as a result of electron impact on this molecule. The overview emission spectrum was measured in the wavelengths within 280 – 950 nm at 50 eV electron energy and is depicted in the Fig. 2. Several emission lines were identified, such as the emission lines of hydrogen's Balmer series - from H_α to H_η , and oxygen emission lines in the IR wavelength region - O I ($3p^5P-3s^5S^0$) and O I ($3p^3P-s^3S^0$) [17]. The most prominent emission bands are the CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) and CH ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Pi$) [18]. The CH ($C^2\Sigma^+-X^2\Pi$) emission was identified as well, but it has weak intensity and is only recognizable in the part of the spectrum where intensity is multiplied 15x (blue line). Additionally, a low-intensity signal from two features of the Swan system C_2 ($d^3\Pi_g-a^3\Pi_u$) [19, 20, 21] was identified along with the C_2 ($C^1\Pi_g-A^1\Pi_u$) emission band that belongs to the Deslandres d'Azambuja system [22, 19, 23, 24]. There are possibly two features corresponding to the emission of the 1st Negative System of N_2^+ ($B^2\Sigma_u^+-X^2\Sigma_g^+$) [25] with observed peaks at 391.3 nm and 427.5 nm. Although nitrogen is not part of the molecular structure of acetone, it probably comes from the air contained in the sample which may also affect the intensity of the oxygen lines in the IR spectral region as well. Based purely on the wavelength, the two features could correspond to C^+ according to [26], but in subsequent measurements of the 3D spectral electron energy map, which will be described later, they were not present in the spectrum recorded at 50 eV, 100 eV, or any other energy. When comparing the spectrum to acetone emission initiated in argon atmospheric plasma jet [11] or laser induced emission [26] we have not detected doubly ionised C^{++} , CO, O^+ . The faint spectral feature between 335 and 340 nm could be attributed to CH_2 [26]. On the other hand, the electron induced spectrum contains very prominent hydrogen Balmer lines from H_α up to H_η which, apart from H_γ , were not identified by Tang et al. [11] nor Okoshi et al. [26].

The wavelength region between 305 and 330 nm is not only occupied by the CH ($C^2\Sigma^+-X^2\Pi$) emission band, but there is also signal detected from the OH ($A^2\Sigma_u^+-X^2\Pi$) $_{(v,v)}$ emission band. Fig. 3 shows a comparison of emission spectra of acetone ($(CH_3)_2CO$) - violet, methane (CH_4) [27] - green and water (H_2O) [8] - red. The emission spectrum of CH_4 contains just signal from CH ($C^2\Sigma^+-X^2\Pi$) while the emission spectrum of H_2O contains signal solely from OH ($A^2\Sigma_u^+-X^2\Pi$). Despite the strong overlap of the OH(A-X) and CH(C-

Transition	Wavelength interval (nm)	Observed peak (nm)
OH ($A^2\Sigma_u^+ - X^2\Pi$)	306.1 - 330	-
CH ($A^2\Delta - X^2\Pi$)	415 - 441.8	-
CH ($B^2\Sigma^- - X^2\Pi$)	386.4 - 401	-
CH ($C^2\Sigma^+ - X^2\Pi$)	305.7 - 323.1	-
C ₂ ($C^1\Pi_g - A^1\Pi_u$)	354.9 - 361.7	-
C ₂ ($d^3\Pi_g - a^3\Pi_u$)	460.3 - 474.3	-
C ₂ ($d^3\Pi_g - a^3\Pi_u$)	500.4 - 520.8	-
H _{α} (3-2)	655.7 - 656.8	656.3
H _{β} (4-2)	485.3 - 486.5	486
H _{γ} (5-2)	433.3 - 434.3	433.9
H _{δ} (6-2)	409.5 - 410.7	410.1
H _{ϵ} (7-2)	396.5 - 397.6	397
H _{ζ} (8-2)	388.4 - 389.4	389.1
H _{η} (9-2)	383 - 384	383.6
O I ($3p^5P - 3s^5S^0$)	776.6 - 777.7	777.3
O I ($3p^3P - 3s^3S^0$)	844.2 - 845	844.7
N ₂ ($B^2\Sigma_u^+ - X^2\Sigma_g^+$) P(0,0)	390.8 - 391.9	391.3
N ₂ ($B^2\Sigma_u^+ - X^2\Sigma_g^+$) P(0,1)	427.0 - 427.9	427.5

Table 1. The transitions observed in the emission spectrum of (CH₃)₂CO.

X) signals, both show distinctive features allowing distinguishing one from another (see Fig. 3). It is apparent that the emission spectrum of acetone contains the features of both CH ($C^2\Sigma^+ - X^2\Pi$) and OH ($A^2\Sigma_u^+ - X^2\Pi$) emission bands. Although there is no OH group in the molecular composition of acetone in its ketone form, acetone can also exist in an enol form as 1-propen-2-ol. However, the concentration of 1-propen-2-ol in an acetone sample naturally does not exceed 0.0001 % [28], which makes it non-detectable by our experimental setup. Despite that, a study on intramolecular hydrogen scrambling processes in acetone in gas phase [29] suggests that there are various possible paths for hydrogen migration within the acetone molecule. The energy barriers for these processes are of the order of several eV, therefore they could be induced by electron interaction. One possible outcome is the formation of COH group and enolization of the molecule. This theoretical model, combined with our experimental results, lead to the conclusion that the hydrogen migration in acetone can be induced by electron impact.

The region within the wavelengths of 380–445 nm is the most active part of the spectrum; therefore, it was measured with higher resolution, corrected for the apparatus sensitivity, and is shown in Fig. 4. Higher resolution measurements lead to the loss of low-intensity features and therefore we have measured only the region where the signal was still detectable. The emission band CH ($A^2\Delta - X^2\Pi$) consists of the (ν, ν) vibrational transitions. Less intensive radiation of CH ($B^2\Sigma^- - X^2\Pi$) emission band is composed purely of (0,0) vibrational transition. As mentioned earlier, several emission lines of hydrogen's Balmer series from H _{γ} to H _{η} were

detected throughout this region as well. Individual rotational transitions from P, Q, R branches of CH fragments were identified according to LIFBASE 2.1.1 spectroscopy tool [30] and Pearse [18]. The nomenclature of the rotational transitions is given by Hund's case a. Relative intensities of the features in the overview spectrum (Fig. 2) and the higher-resolution interval (Fig. 4) may differ. This is caused by the difference in the resolution of the spectra. It is most visible comparing emission lines and emission bands, e.g. H_γ emission line and the Q1 branch of the CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) emission band.

The emission spectrum of acetone within the wavelength range of 380–450 nm was further recorded at several electron energies, ranging from 10 eV to 100 eV in 5 eV increments. These spectra form a 3D spectral electron energy map for transitions within the selected spectral range. The graph of the acetone spectra is presented in Fig. 5.

Relative excitation-emission functions of H_β , H_γ and Q1 branch of CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) were measured in the electron energy range within 10 – 100 eV using the photomultiplier as detector. The functions are shown in Fig. 6. The excitation-emission function measured at 433.9 nm (Fig. 6b) contains the signal from H_γ emission line as well as CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) emission band, that radiates at the same wavelength. In order to obtain the excitation-emission function purely for H_γ , the contribution from CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) needs to be subtracted. We assume that the excitation-emission function of CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) emission band has the same progression and shape throughout its whole wavelength region. Hence, the excitation-emission function of CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) measured at 430.8 nm (Fig. 6c) can be used for the subtraction after adjusting its relative intensity to the intensity of the emission band at 433.9 nm. The adjustment of the relative intensity of the excitation emission function is done by multiplying its intensity by the ratio of the intensity of the excitation-emission function of CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) (Fig. 6c) at 50 eV and the intensity of the 50 eV emission spectrum at 434.2 nm (Fig. 4b). The intensity at this wavelength is considered to be similar to the real intensity of CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) at 433.9 nm. The excitation-emission function of H_γ after the subtraction is depicted in (Fig. 6d).

4. Conclusion

The acetone emission induced by low-energy electron impact has been analysed. The busiest spectral region between 380 and 445 nm was analysed in detail and 3D spectral electron energy map of this region has been constructed for the energy range 10-100 eV. Based on the distinctive shape of the CH(C-X) and OH(A-X) spectral features we have shown that the electron impact on acetone causes migration of hydrogen and formation of the OH group which is not present in the molecule before the reaction. For the selected most prominent excited products the excitation-emission curves were determined. The exact emission data were included as a supplementary allowing extraction of the emission spectra or excitation-emission curves from the 3D spectral electron energy map.

5. Acknowledgments

This paper is dedicated to the scientific achievements of Professor Tilmann Märk, on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

This work was supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under the Contracts no. SK-PL-23-0050, APVV-19-0386 and APVV-23-0522, Slovak grant agency VEGA under projects nr. 1/0489/21 and 1/0553/22. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871149 and was also partially supported by CU Grant 2024 nr. UK/3226/2024.

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Figure 1. Scheme of the electron induced fluorescence experimental apparatus. Blue – electron beam, red – fluorescence signal, violet – molecular beam. TEM – Trochoidal electron monochromator, PMT – Photomultiplier.

Figure 2. The emission spectrum of dissociated fragments of $(CH_3)_2CO$ measured at 50 eV. Blue line - spectrum intensity multiplied by the factor of 15.

Figure 3. Comparison acetone ($(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$) emission spectrum - violet, methane (CH_4) [27] - green and water (H_2O) [8] - red. In this spectral region the OH(A-X) and CH(C-X) signals overlap, but each of them has distinctive features distinguishing one from another. The acetone spectrum contains the features corresponding to both CH(C-X) and OH(A-X) transitions proving the hydrogen migration in acetone induced by electron impact.

Figure 4. Higher resolution emission spectrum of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$ measured at 50 eV and calibrated for apparatus sensitivity. The rotational structures were identified according to [30].

Figure 5. The 3D spectral graph of emission spectrum of acetone measured at multiple electron energies ranging from 10 to 100 eV.

Figure 6. Excitation-emission functions of: a) H_{β} at 486 nm, b) H_{γ} combined with CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) at 433.9 nm, c) Q1 branch of CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) at 430.8 nm, d) H_{γ} with subtracted signal from CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) at 433.9 nm

Supplementary material

Dissociative excitation of acetone induced by electron impact

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September 2024

Figure 7. The excitation emission function of H_{η} at 383.7 nm obtained from the 3D spectral graph.

Figure 8. The excitation emission function of CH (B-X) (0,0) at 387.4 nm obtained from the 3D spectral graph.

Figure 9. The excitation emission function of H_{ζ} at 389.1 nm obtained from the 3D spectral graph.

Figure 10. The excitation emission function of H_{ϵ} at 397 nm obtained from the 3D spectral graph.

Figure 11. The excitation emission function of H_{δ} at 410.1 nm obtained from the 3D spectral graph.

Figure 12. The excitation emission function of CH (A-X)(v,v) at 430.8 nm obtained from the 3D spectral graph.

Figure 13. The excitation emission function of CH (A-X)(2,2) at 432.1 nm obtained from the 3D spectral graph.

Figure 14. The excitation emission function of H_γ at 433.9 nm obtained from the 3D spectral graph.